

VELOCITY CONSTANTS OF CHEMICAL REACTIONS FROM SPECTROSCOPIC DATA OF MOLECULES

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A new relation, reported in an earlier communication, correlating the velocity constants of chemical reactions with the spectroscopic data of the reacting molecules, has been applied successfully to calculate the specific reaction rates of a few decomposition reactions. The values of $\ln v_0$ in the new equation, which corresponds to $\ln A$ in the Arrhenius equation are in the same range as values of $\ln A$ in the Arrhenius equation. The specific reaction rates of decomposition of bromine, chlorine, iodine, oxygen, sodium and nitrogen molecules have been calculated and the values obtained are in agreement with what one would expect from the respective bond strengths of the molecules.

Perrin (*Ann. phys.*, 1919, 11, 5), Dushman (*J. Franklin Inst.*, 1920, 189, 515) and Rice and McKeown (*Phil. Mag.*, 1923, 46, 471) have made attempts to correlate radiation frequencies with velocity constants of chemical reactions. These endeavours have, however, been proved inadequate (Langmuir, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2190; Christiansen and Kramers, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 104, 451; Lindemann, *Phil. Mag.*, 1920, 40, 671). In a recent communication (Mathur, unpublished, a theory has been advanced and a new relationship obtained between the radiation frequencies and the velocity constants of thermal and photochemical reactions:

$$k = v_0 \cdot e^{-Nh(v_{\text{conv}} - \nu_0)/RT} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where v_{conv} is the convergence limit in the absorption spectrum of the decomposing molecules, ν_0 , the electronic excitation frequency (Herzberg, "Molecular Spectra and Molecular Structure", D. Van Nostrand Co., Inc., N.Y., 1953, p. 444), T , the absolute temperature and N , h and R , the Avogadro number, Planck's constant and the gas constant respectively; k is the velocity constant. The values of v_{conv} and ν_0 for several molecules have been obtained in the earlier communication (Mathur, *loc. cit.*) from kinetics data. In the present one the velocity constants of decomposition reactions of a few molecules have been calculated from the spectroscopic data available for them. The data recorded in Table I have been taken from "Physical Chemistry" by Moelwyn Hughes (p. 409). In Table I v_{conv} represents convergence limit, E_{atom} in wave numbers corresponding to ν_0 , and D'' is the activation energy equaling to $Nh(v_{\text{conv}} - \nu_0)$ in equation (1). So equation (1) can be written as

$$k = [E_{\text{atom}} \times c] \cdot e^{-D''/RT} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where c is the velocity of light. Taking logarithms,

$$2.303 \log k = 2.303 \log (c \times E_{\text{atom}}) - \frac{D''}{RT} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

TABLE I

Mol.	v_{conv}/c (cm^{-1}).	E_{atom} (cm^{-1}).	D'' (Calc./g. mol.).	Mol.	v_{conv}/c (cm^{-1}).	E_{atom} (cm^{-1}).	D'' (Calc./g. mol.).
O_2	57,110	15,890	117,300	I_2	20,037	7,598	35,380
Cl_2	20,893	881	56,760	Na_2	23,100	16,930	17,520
Br_2	19,575	3,685	45,210	N_2	121,100	19,215 } 28,855 }	207,500

The velocity constants of the decomposition of N_2 , O_2 , Cl_2 , Br_2 , I_2 and Na_2 molecules at different temperatures, calculated from the data in Table I, are listed in Table II. The rates of decomposition of nitrogen, oxygen etc. at different temperatures, listed in Table II, are in conformity with what one may expect from the respective bond strengths of these molecules. It is interesting to note that the temperature of decomposition of various molecules corresponding to a high reaction rate of the order of 0.0372 to 0.0700 vary in a regular sequence. Nitrogen attains this rate at a temperature as high as 2800°K, while Na_2 at a temperature as low as 240°K.

TABLE II

Temp.	k (sec ⁻¹).	Temp.	k (sec ⁻¹).	Temp.	k (sec ⁻¹).
Nitrogen.		Oxygen.		Chlorine.	
2400° K	7.423×10^{-5}	1100° K	2.389×10^{-9}	600° K	5.780×10^{-3}
2500°	4.272×10^{-4}	1150°	2.501×10^{-8}	650°	2.249×10^{-2}
2600°	2.092×10^{-3}	1200°	2.128×10^{-7}	700°	5.151×10^{-2}
2700°	9.345×10^{-3}	1300°	9.080×10^{-6}	750°	7.796×10^{-2}
2800°	3.720×10^{-2}	1400°	2.334×10^{-5}	800°	8.354×10^{-2}
2900°	1.351×10^{-1}	1500°	3.064×10^{-5}	850°	6.790×10^{-2}
3000°	4.439×10^{-1}	1600°	4.551×10^{-5}		
Bromine.		Iodine.		Sodium.	
450°	1.240×10^{-8}	300°	3.869×10^{-12}	190°	3.673×10^{-5}
500°	1.964×10^{-6}	350°	1.852×10^{-9}	200°	3.720×10^{-5}
550°	1.212×10^{-4}	400°	1.097×10^{-7}	210°	2.989×10^{-5}
600°	3.831×10^{-3}	450°	1.505×10^{-6}	220°	2.021×10^{-5}
650°	7.134×10^{-2}	500°	7.90×10^{-6}	230°	1.163×10^{-5}
				240°	5.697×10^{-6}

It is important to note that the spectroscopic values of $\log v_0$ obtained for the above mentioned reactions (Table III) lie between a range which corresponds to values of $\log A$ for most of the reactions calculated from chemical data (Hinschelwood, "Kinetics of Chemical Change", Oxford University Press, pp. 119-125) using the Arrhenius equation.

TABLE III

Molecule.	$\log_0 (E_{atom} \times c)$.	Molecule.	$\log_0 A$
Chlorine	30.90	Nitrogen pentoxide decomposition	31.45
Bromine	32.32	Azopropane ⁱ	31.65
Iodine	33.07	Acetone	34.34
Oxygen	33.82	Phosgene	34.85
Sodium	33.68	Azomethane	36.73
Nitrogen	33.09		